

FACTORS INFLUENCING OPTIMIZATION BASKETBALL REFEREE MANAGEMENT IN HUNAN PROVINCE CHINA

LI CHEN

Doctoral Student, Innovation Management College, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University.
Email: s63484950008@ssru.ac.th, 251923380@qq.com

SUPITR SAMAHITO

PhD, Innovation Management College, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok.
Email: supitr.sa@ssru.ac.th

MONTIPA VILASTHIP

Lecturer, College of Innovation and Management, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University.
Email: montipa.vi@ssru.ac.th

Abstract

Since the invention of basketball in 1892, it has been 120 years of history, the founder of basketball rules James Naismith issued 13 simple rules in the "Triangle" magazine, marking the basketball into the full confrontation game stage, and introduced the referee as the leader of the game organization and the "judge" of the fair implementation of the rules. In China and most countries, basketball referees are amateur staff, which means that they are not mainly engaged in refereeing work, with the rapid development of CBA/WCBA professional league, the need for professional referees is becoming more and more urgent. With the improvement of people's living standards and the rise of the national fitness trend, the development trend of basketball in China is becoming increasingly obvious. As an indispensable part, referees assume important responsibilities. In China's professional league, there is still a big gap in the ability of referees, which is a very necessary and urgent task for the overall ability improvement of referees, the reform of management system and training mechanism.

Keywords: Referee Mangement, Influencing, Factors.

1. POLICY SUPPORT OF HUNAN PROVINCIAL GOVERNMENT

Hunan Province has always attached great importance to the development of basketball. As a strong sports province, in order to further promote the prosperity of basketball, the government has introduced a series of support measures, which are included in the overall strategy of building a sports power in an all-round way. In terms of strengthening the construction of the basketball referee team, the government attaches great importance to improving the professional level and quality of referees, organizing various training courses, seminars and other activities to continuously improve the technical ability and law enforcement level of referees, increasing the reward of excellent referees, and encouraging them to maintain the principle of fairness, fairness and openness in the game. The government introduced these measures to comprehensively improve the overall strength of Hunan's basketball industry, and make Hunan an important force in China and even the world's basketball. Based on this, this paper will combine the method of normative analysis and empirical analysis to understand the current situation of Hunan basketball referee management.

2. ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT SITUATION OF TRAINING MODE OF BASKETBALL REFEREES IN HUNAN PROVINCE

2.1 Analysis of ways and methods of referees' learning

In the investigation of referees, the initial training units in the process of learning referees themselves, 111 referees from colleges and universities, 75 referees are trained by the city and state basketball association. It can be seen that colleges and universities and various cities and states have sent a large number of reserve talents for the basketball referee team in our province, which is the main force to train the reserve force of referees.

In the process of learning basketball referees in colleges and universities, 41% of students learn through their own basketball clubs; 12% of the students learn referee knowledge under the guidance of teachers who have experience in judging when there is no club in the school; 23% of students have basketball referee courses in their schools. Another 20% of students study by themselves. Referees in colleges and universities have more spare time to systematically learn basketball referees, in their age group, the ability to accept new things is strong, is the golden age to learn basketball referees.

A referee usually has more than one training stage, through the investigation of referees, 84% of referees have experienced the training of provincial and municipal basketball associations, 70% of referees have experienced the training of colleges and universities, and the proportion of students receiving the training of provincial and municipal basketball associations is the largest, because the student referees who study in colleges and universities, if they do not continue to teach in colleges and universities after graduation. I want to continue to love the work of basketball referees, and eventually I want to return to the city and state basketball association, which also sends fresh blood to our city and state basketball Association.

Nowadays, resources and information are developed, and there are many ways to obtain information. Due to the influence of various factors such as study and work, referees are not limited to only one way to learn basketball referees. In the process of learning basketball referees, there are various ways to acquire knowledge. Among them, 90% of referees learn professional knowledge mainly from reference-related books, and the most authoritative book is the "Basketball Referee Manual" prepared by the Chinese Basketball Association, which is the fastest way to learn basketball referees. Basketball referees are also a highly practical job, and judging matches is also a way to quickly improve their own level, 87% of referees are in the game to learn the professional knowledge of referees. 82% increase the understanding of referees' professional knowledge through mutual communication and learning among referees; Referee work is originally a team work, in a game is through the cooperation of two or three people to complete the game, which also promotes the communication between referees must communicate; In the competition system, the referees live together in a few days of the game, which also better promotes everyone to have a lot of time to communicate, learn and share, and improve together. Nowadays, there are abundant information resources in various media, 79% of referees learn through TV broadcasts and media materials. Learning gestures, positioning and penalty standards of referees in high-level competitions is also a kind of improvement for

themselves. 55% and 52% of referees get the latest knowledge through regular and pre-match training, and 40% learn through online communication. In short, there are many ways to learn the professional knowledge of referees, and referees of all stages can find the corresponding learning ways.

2.2 Analysis of funding sources for referees' participation in training

According to the visit, the promotion or learning training courses for basketball referees in Hunan Province are issued by the basketball associations, and the referees voluntarily sign up for learning. 83% of referees attend training courses at their own expense; 13% of referees are funded by the unit to participate in the training, and most of these referees are school teachers. Individual schools have certain financial support for participating in such learning activities. Among them, 4% of the referees are paid by the organizer, and most of these referees are referee lecturers or high-level referees. It can be seen that Hunan provincial basketball referees participate in training, mostly at their own expense to participate in referee training, it can be seen that our provincial referees for their own business level improvement demands are still very high, everyone is relying on the love of basketball referees to voluntarily participate in training, and often insufficient funds are difficult to support the standardized development of the referee team.

2.3 Analysis of referees' training content and participation times

Participating in the referee training class, not only can learn the latest theoretical knowledge, but also in the training process, communicate with the referee colleagues to learn from each other, is an important way to improve their own level. In our province, the content of each training for referees can be roughly divided into theoretical learning and practical learning, and finally carry out periodic assessment. The theoretical study includes: the theoretical study of three-on-three basketball, the theoretical study of small basketball, the English knowledge of referees and the professional ethics of referees. The practical learning includes: the referee's basic gesture training, the referee's position selection and movement, the interpretation of a single movement, video case learning and physical fitness.

2.4 Analysis of teacher strength of referee training

Table 1: Information table of Hunan Provincial basketball referee training referee instructor

name	rank	training content	Adjudication experience
Li Xue Jun	nternational class	Practice and training of referee method	28year
Wu Yubo	national level	Interpretation of the law of judgment theory	12year
Li Xun	national level	Three-man basketball rules	10year
Peng Kun	national level	Small basketball rules explain	8year

When we carry out the promotion assessment of referees in our province, we will carry out training work. After the training work is completed, we will carry out theoretical, physical and practical promotion assessment of referees. Through the interview with Du Xiyuan, director of the Hunan Basketball Association Committee, we learned that the training of referees is an

indispensable part of the development of basketball in our province. Referees' lecturers play a leading role in the learning process of referees, and the level of referees' lecturers also affects the level of referees to some extent. Our lecturer team of Hunan Basketball Association is composed of league referees who have high level of executive judgment ability, high level of theoretical ability and high level of teaching ability.

As can be seen from the table, each field has an experienced referee teacher as a lecturer. During the interview with the experts of the Basketball Association, I learned that because there are more people from various places participating in the training, all the participating referees will be divided into groups ranging from 10-20 people, and experienced national referees will be appointed as the team leader to assume the management responsibility during the training.

2.5 Continuing education of referees

With the continuous development of basketball, the rules are constantly changing. Referees, as the embodiment of the rules on the court, guide a basketball game to develop in the right direction, which requires us to have high requirements on the theoretical level and practical ability of referees, and require referees to constantly update their theoretical knowledge base in peacetime. In every province and city, the first-level referees are the middle force in our basketball referees team, they often have been engaged in the referee work for a period of time, there is a certain degree of experience in the referee, but in the details of the referee and the mastery of the game is often unclear, there is still a lot of room for improvement.

Through the interview with Jiang Nan, Secretary-General of Hunan Basketball Association, I learned that in terms of the continuing education of referees, training courses will be held from time to time in the province, annual registration of referees will be conducted, and high-level referees lecturers in the province will be hired to give lectures on the latest changes in basketball rules and the latest application of referee law. Perform physical tests on referees. Another way to get information is to introduce the new rules at the referees' joint meeting before the tournament, where experienced referees or technical representatives will be present. The development of basketball sports in cities and states is also inseparable from the grassroots referees in cities and states, through the author's conversation with the referees in cities and states in the competition area, the basketball association that regularly carries out the training of referees can also account for a small part.

It can be seen that, for the continuing education of referees in our province, the offline training is not carried out regularly, the form of training is relatively limited, and the training lacks a certain system and stage; As a referee at the forefront of the rules, the referee should continue to learn and popularize new theories and knowledge, and systematically carry out continuing education of the referee, which has played a positive role in promoting the construction of the referee team in Hunan Province, and is also the center of the construction of the referee team in Hunan Province. Therefore, it is very necessary to carry out continuing education of the referee.

3. CONCLUSIONS

3.1 Most referees in Hunan Province were initially graded by universities, followed by local basketball associations; Training participants are mostly self-funded, mainly in the form of offline training and pre-competition training. The training time is short, theoretical training accounts for the majority of the training content, and the training time and the number of trainings are not fixed. The training content lacks the module of on-the-spot execution practice. The way of training is lack of systematic, continuity and standardization, and the content and way of training are too single.

3.2 In the management of basketball referees in Hunan Province, the function division of the management department is not clear; The way of selecting materials is single; The selection of referees is too one-sided; The reward and punishment system needs to be improved; Lack of supervision and control of referees on and off the court; There is also a lack of clear criteria for promotion grades; The information management of referees in the province is not perfect, and some information is still missing.

4. SUGGESTIONS

4.1 In terms of referee training content and theory teaching in Hunan Province, it is not only a simple classroom teaching form, but should be taught in combination with practice, and more training should be added to the practice of on-the-spot execution and emphasis should be placed on the teaching of basic referee skills; The time and frequency of training should be carried out regularly to avoid the fault of the knowledge structure of the referee; In the form of training, multi-space, multi-dimensional and all-round development can be adopted, such as online teaching, assigning offline homework, setting up offline training courses, building communication platforms for referees, etc., to broaden the way for referees to obtain knowledge sources.

4.2 In terms of the management of basketball referees in Hunan Province, first of all, the administrative department, Hunan Basketball Referee Committee, should play a leading role in detailing the work of various functional departments under the committee, with a clear division of labor and a detailed point; In the arrangement of on-court referees, we should boldly use young referees to enforce key matches, exercise their psychological quality and make them grow rapidly. In terms of promotion, everyone has equal opportunities, promotion assessment should be open, fair and transparent, avoid vicious competition, so that capable referees have promotion opportunities, and ensure the healthy development of Hunan basketball referees team; Finally, it is necessary to use the information big data platform to establish a referee information database in Hunan Province, carry out information management of referees in our province, master the basic information of referees, the number of years, the level of referees and other data, and more convenient for the selection, on-field appointment, evaluation and other management work of referees.

References

- 1) Hao, P. (2014). Research on the status quo investigation and countermeasures of basketball referee training system in Jiangsu Province (Master's thesis). Jiangsu: Yangzhou University
- 2) Jiang, W,N.(2017). Investigation on the development Status and training Mode of Key youth basketball referees in Jiangsu Province (Master thesis). Jiangsu: Soochow University.
- 3) Li, Y,W. (2017). Research on the development status and Countermeasures of Basketball referees in Xinjiang (Master's thesis). Xinjiang: Xinjiang Normal University.
- 4) Han,T,H.(2019). Research on the Current Situation and development Trend of Basketball Referees in Shanxi Province (Master thesis). Shanxi: Shanxi University.

Journal Article

- 1) Chu,L,X & Hong,G,W&Wan,Y,C.(2013).Research on Human Resource Management of Athletic Sports in China.Beijing. Sports Culture Guide,2005,25(1):19-22.
- 2) Liu,L & Qiu,Y,J.(2012).The Development History and Prospect of Human Resource Management in Sports in China.Chengdu.Sichuan Sports Science, 22 (4): 10 -15.
- 3) Li,Y,F & Wei,G,X & Chen,G.(2005).The impact of the modern technological revolution on human resource management in sports in China. Shenyang. Journal of Shenyang Sports Institute,24(2):42-44.
- 4) Xiao,L,P.(2005).Research on Human Resource Regulation and Sustainable Development of Chinese Competitive Sports. Guangzhou. Journal of Guangzhou Sports Institute,25(1):19-22.